

UNDER X-RAY IRRADIATION

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Relevance: It has been shown that the effect of X-ray irradiation at 2 Gy and 4 Gy leads to suppression of the activity of the studied enzymes in various brain structures. Moreover, it was found that pre-administration of saffron extract in many cases prevents significant suppression of the studied enzymes by irradiation, and on the contrary, this antioxidant promotes an increase in their activity in brain structures. Objective: To study the effect of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) stigma extract on the dynamics of changes in the content of different types of surface-exposed SH-groups, structurally masked protein SH-groups, and glutathione under X-ray irradiation at doses of 2 and 4 Gy in different brain regions.

Materials and Methods:

The study was conducted on male rats weighing 180 ± 20 g. The experimental design was as follows:

- Group I – control
- Group II – X-ray irradiation
- Group III – saffron extract + X-ray irradiation

For 21 days prior to irradiation, animals received saffron extract per os at a dose of 120 mg/kg. Measurements were taken 1 hour, 3 days, and 6 days after irradiation. X-ray irradiation was performed using the "RUM-17" device at doses of 2 Gy and 4 Gy. The content of various SH-groups in homogenates was determined according to Ellman G.L. as modified by Sedlak J. and Lindsay R.N. (1968) [2, 3]. The method is based on the reaction of 5,5'-dithiobis(2-nitrobenzoic acid) with aliphatic thiol compounds at pH 8.0, forming 1 mole of 2-nitro-5-mercaptobenzoic acid per mole of thiol. The anion of this acid has an intense yellow color, which is used for spectrophotometric determination of thiol compound concentrations

Results: Data were processed by Student's t-test. Results showed that X-ray irradiation leads to a decrease in thiol group levels in the body. The antioxidant system is unable to fully compensate for the effects of radiation exposure, therefore external radioprotectors are required.

Conclusions: Thus, in the studied brain structures, X-ray irradiation (4 Gy) caused a reduction in thiol group content depending on the observation time. Administration of saffron extract stabilizes thiol group concentrations and protects against the oxidative effects of free radical compounds, which are intensified by irradiation.